

Redefining Entrepreneurship in Research through Intellectual Asset Valorisation and Standardisation

IAM4RE.eu is a brand-new EU-funded action for Public Research Organisations and Academic Institutions to boost intellectual asset management (IAM) and standardisation.

In today's dynamic and innovative environment, intangible assets are at the heart of the use of R&D results and impact. IAM4RE.eu aligns closely with the **EU's push for open science, sustainable innovation**, and the **valorisation of publicly funded research**, contributing to the broader goals of the **European Research Area (ERA)**. The project also complements initiatives such as the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)** and efforts to improve **research impact pathways** through standardisation.

Many public research organisations (PROs) and academic institutions (Acls) across Europe still find it very challenging to recognise, manage, and leverage these assets to their full potential. EC wants to further support and empower institutions and so **IAM4RE.eu – Intellectual Asset Management for Research and Entrepreneurship** – is here to help.

Redefining Knowledge Valorisation and supporting Europe's Innovation agenda

The General Principles of Knowledge Valorisation, published by the EC in 2022, reinforce the scope of impacts arising from the complexity and richness of research outcomes. IAM4RE.eu therefore focuses on the broader concept of Intellectual Asset Management, encompassing not only patents and licenses, but also **know-how, data, software, methodologies, standards**, and more.

To unlock this potential, IAM4RE.eu will provide research institutions with practical tools, tailored training, and strategic guidance to maximise the value of their intangible assets. The project is fully aligned with the [EU Code of Practice on Smart Use of Intellectual Assets](#) and the use of standards as described in the Code of Practice on [Standardisation](#), ensuring its outcomes are impactful, policy-relevant, and widely applicable.

"IAM4RE.eu represents a timely opportunity to support European research players with the tools to needed to fully make use of their knowledge assets. There is still a gap between research and entrepreneurship. Through this initiative we aim to boost a more strategic, sustainable, and inclusive approach to knowledge valorisation", says **Andrea di Anselmo**, IAM4RE.eu Project Coordinator at META Group.

By developing a comprehensive support framework, the action will help institutions integrate IAM into their daily operations and long-term strategies, promoting **sustainable innovation** and amplifying their **societal and economic contributions**.

Key objectives and approach

IAM4RE.eu is built around five core objectives: (i) **Simplify knowledge valorisation and standardisation** through modular educational content; (ii) **Strengthen institutional capacity** with real-world training tailored to the needs of PROs and Acls; (iii) **Support intermediaries** (Technology Transfer Offices, research support staff, incubators) through a dedicated Train-the-Trainer approach; (iv) **Promote the adoption of EU Codes of Practice**, ensuring their integration into institutional strategies and operations; and (v) **Ensure the long-term sustainability and scalability** of the project's outcomes through community building, policy engagement, exploitation and dissemination strategies.

Practical tools for real-world change

The IAM4RE.eu action has a strong focus on **capacity-building** and will design and deliver a suite of practical tools and resources to support research institutions. This includes a **training suite tailored to**

diverse audiences, a **Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)**, a comprehensive **Train-the-Trainer programme**, new **service formats** to support institutional implementation, and **policy guidelines** for decision-makers within **Public Research Organisations (PROs)**. These tools will undergo **real-world testing** in pilot institutions to ensure they are not only **theoretically sound** but also **practically effective**.

A collaborative partnership for the future

IAM4RE.eu is a Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action, [funded under the HORIZON-CL4-2024-HUMAN-02-35](#) topic by the [European Commission](#) and managed by [HADEA \(European Health and Digital Executive Agency\)](#). Over 24 months, a consortium of leading organisations from across Europe will guide the project forward: [META Group \(Coord.\)](#), [ASTP](#), [COMMpla Srl \(AE\)](#), [EURICE](#), [META BE \(AE\)](#), [RISE](#), [TRUST-IT](#), [UBFON](#), [Vilnius University \(VU\)](#). Together, these partners bring a wealth of expertise in innovation management, technology transfer, policy development, communication, and stakeholder engagement, creating a solid foundation for IAM4RE.eu's success.

This is only the beginning – Follow us for the latest updates!

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Intellectual Asset Management for
Research & Entrepreneurship